

REFLECTIONS ON PEDAGOGY AND PEDAGOGUES: PRACTICAL AND THEORETICAL INTERMITTENCES

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ABSTRACT

This essay aims to present reflections on learning processes. This is a bibliographic study, based on analytical hermeneutics. As a methodology, for the accomplishment of this study, the analyzes were carried through researches in books, considering the main aspects and approaches on the contributions of the research on the learning. The knowledge and condition that the contemporary moment presents to man, of being able to manipulate his conquests in relation to time, also made him a hostage of this moment, believing that he is a being of supernatural intelligence, being above the natural condition of being and living. Curiosity and the desire to know and understand things is a human attribute, universal, characterized as a phylogenetic inheritance and not an event that appears as a product of modern human thought and, the most interesting thing is that, there is a certain period in human history in which the creation of myths, which are fabulous explanations about the origin of the universe and about the organic and mechanical occurrences within it, were drastically reduced, which removed the common human being from a possibility of understanding his existence in the Cosmos. It was found that according to the current condition, learning and teaching are different phases of the same progressive and continuous mechanism. Through the results of the research, it can be said that one of the challenges in the educational context is not just knowing how to teach or how to evaluate, but to present knowledge in a way that the student learns and develops better.

Keywords: Pedagogy and Pedagogues. Empiricism. Didactics. Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Each society created its own value criteria to determine what it considered as formal education, develop its principles and manage the processes, giving it the necessary dynamism

to develop and maintain itself as something to be remembered in the future, as a nation, as a body and not as an individual. It was the communities, tribes, phratries and, later, the Polis (Greek city-states) that presented themselves as powerful, not a single being, other than the sovereign municipal god.

The issue of knowing how to read and write represented something complex, not very desired, because such an action did not yield strong memories in the future. Everyone, almost without exception, wanted to be warriors, fight in great battles and be immortalized for their heroic deeds. Therefore, when it is stated that education, in Antiquity, was entirely based on the cult of the body and preparation for war, it is to ignore the empirical nuances that involve a war campaign strategy, with a view to it being successful. Anyone who dared to lose a war was condemned to lose everything, from their home, their freedom to their life and also be condemned to dishonor and eternal oblivion.

The older generations had the obligation to prepare their children and grandchildren to take care of their lands and their women and, especially, children, protecting them with their lives and, in a space where there were no activities that required specialties. of writing and reading, as long as one knew how *to recount* heroic deeds and, for that purpose, an accurate memory was already sufficient, education, in the complex and theoretical ways that are conceived and known today and that are applied in the formation of individuals, was unthinkable, because it was innocuous at the time, as it continues to be.

The only thing that has not changed is the attribute of knowledge transfer, which continues to be a characteristic that has been improved over time, with the emergence of more sophisticated equipment and instruments. But, as Gramsci states (*apud* Ruiz, 1988, p. 8), “like Lao-Tse of the Chinese legend, we are old children, people who are born at the age of eighty. A circle of traditions passes over us, and we must bend our hearts to support it: centuries-old laws bind our current activity and the effort to overcome them must synthesize all the efforts of past generations”.

The author urges that, in order to overcome tradition and we do not know why the Italian philosopher hated the system so much, in order to destroy it, creating another in his image and likeness, the solution would be knowledge of all the generations and the thinking that they adopted as their particular ideological principles. This is the most complex task of a sociological study, because what motivated each people to build their unique and particular form of learning, through which it enabled the transmission of knowledge that shapes their social identity, is the link that can allow them to come closer to the understanding of the entire sociological problem.

It is not something that contemporary education has managed to condition to students, with their curricula increasingly full of useless and meaningless things, given that the family, which was the first and great building force of the human personological structure, had its right and its disciplinary duties hijacked by the State and relegated to individuals who are strangers to children, in which the absence of emotional ties hinders learning performance.

To make matters worse, these individuals who assume the position of teachers, of masters, present their own versions of life and their ideologies and beliefs, such as law and power, and in those brief moments everything seems beautiful and wonderful, because they reveal a rebellious world, a cause against a type of control that limits a wild mind without much perception of reality. This is the danger! Not for teenagers, but for teachers who translate that whole game of rebellion and conflict, love and hate against parents and the system as the most authentic existential attitude and, based on this bestial reading, books and seminars are produced on a Fordist scale, seeming like a given reality.

Everything that is produced in the field of science is the product of the deductive thought of some thinker who starts from empirical situations towards the construction of something that can shed light on what lies outside the sphere of his epistemic domain. One cannot lose sight of the fact that it is up to the researcher to systematically observe and faithfully record facts and phenomena until they have enough time to seek answers through experiences. This is because each object, in particular, has a unique psychology that does not change over time, clarifying that what undergoes changes are the processes of analysis and interpretation that are being innovated and expanded, thus allowing a greater capacity for vision about what if you intend to study scientifically.

It is not about seeing man as a being limited in time and space, much less trying to see him as an exalted entity that is beyond good and evil. Each advance that you look at over time is the result of previous advances that, thanks to the conditions of clarification they provided, allow the elaboration of increasingly deeper doubts and questions and this becomes possible thanks to the knowledge that is produced by previous generations and transmitted to the next future generations.

IS HUMAN BEING AN OPPORTUNITY FOR A NEW BEGINNING?

Thinking of the human being who is born as a new beginning is placing him as the center of everything that exists in the universe; It's believing that the whole world would stop, simply because a new being arrived on Earth, and that's not exactly how it works. Each time someone

comes to light is a rare opportunity for the universe to continue its march towards new structures of production and re-production of processes essential to the existence, not just of man, but of an entire physical chain.

Claiming that man destroys nature and that, with his action, he is condemning it to disappear is another innocence; It's giving too much power to someone who takes years to learn to speak in an organized way and whose brain has matured after decades of life. When comparing the human being with other animals in nature, what becomes clear is that the intellectual capacity that was provided to him does not represent an occasional fact, but rather a determination of a much superior entity and which he already knew would do his tricks and which, in order to keep things within equitable standards, allows nature some *natural catastrophes*, just to make the administrator return to his professional itinerary.

Foucault (1996) argues that man, at birth, is the most incompetent being known and the meaning of this expression must be understood in his motor and physical disability when compared to other living beings in nature. The Arabs already expressed this same perception, starting from the empirical observation of wild and domestic animals and men since they were born, requiring the most basic to the most complex care, such as medical care, insertion of foreign bodies into their bodies, in order to that can create organic resistance.

All of this is an essential component of human education and, according to Kant (2001), man is the only creature that needs to be educated. Understanding education as care (sustenance, maintenance), discipline and instruction, together with personological training. It is always difficult to make people understand that wisdom and logical knowledge are not transmitted via DNA; this is a product of the action of the environment, education and the effort of each person to master the aspects that are around them and understand the phenomena that occur in nature and with individuals. What a generation inherited from its predecessors is improved, improved, expanded, according to needs and possibilities and all of this is transferred to the next generation, which faces the same challenge of increasing its scope of action, according to the challenges. posed by nature and society.

It must always be very clear that, for Kant, education is a term that refers to the concept of discipline, therefore, when stating that *one generation educates another*, he is saying, loudly and clearly, that the one that precedes has the obligation to ensure for the good customs of those who follow them in time and space. When this task is not fulfilled with due rigor, what we have is the emergence of a bestial posture, the manifestation of the animality that exists within every human being, which, in the Prussian philosopher's conception, represents the imminent failure of education in society. preparation of human beings for a civilized life and society.

Each society prepares its students, through school, according to the ideology it defends. If, at all times, there have been fierce disputes and insane wars, [*apparently*] understood as being meaningless, it is because this represented the desire of the masses and, when this same society stood up against such abuses, it was because its ego was already satisfied. and the commander was unable to perform the reading, being dragged by his own insanity into the black hole of madness and dissatisfaction that always told him it wasn't enough.

Regarding this, Kant reveals that education converts the innate instinctive condition into rationality, which must be worked on from a very early age, guiding the individual so that they can understand the first and, thus, understand the second. It is impossible for someone to reach the level of mastery of a feeling if they do not know what that thing is about, what causes it, what makes it awaken and what makes it disappear. In this sense, instincts become dominating chains that need to be transformed into objects of systematic studies, subject to phenomenological analysis until the degree of sapience about their reason for being is reached. And, what does all this have to do with intellectual education? This is the point of honor, because education as we know it is a mark designed to tame wild human thinking; as this is something impossible to be, a transmutation occurs, in which these are sublimated into cathexial energy aimed at technical learning and this knowledge, which is a refined product of a voracious situation, can be presented to civilized society as an instrument of pride and passion.

Neither the arena nor the opponents change, just the rules. This has been built since man comes to term, in the form of a defenseless baby. The newborn has an extremely limited range of knowledge. Until the fifth month of life, he doesn't even know his own mother. Birth is a serious trauma for him...; during its intrauterine life, the child breathed and now must learn to breathe; had a physical environment in constant heat, protected from sudden shocks and violent stimuli, and now, after birth, he finds himself in an environment with a lower temperature, with possibilities of even violent falls, in addition to intense and variable light and auditory stimulants .

The knowledge and condition that the contemporary moment presents to man, of being able to manipulate his achievements in relation to time, also made him a hostage of this moment, believing that he is a being of supernatural intelligence, being above the natural condition of being and being. Every time someone misses the opportunity to see themselves reflected in the mirror of reality, they end up looking for justifications to explain their cowardice in the face of life and, strangely enough, they never manage to convince even themselves about their condition of fear of daring to go further. than where you are. The current existence, in which life calls for boldness, requires proactivity in terms of creativity and technical resourcefulness,

comparing new procedures with those currently in force and what can be rescued from the recent and more distant past.

Society crossed its thinking from one extreme to another, in which it went from paranoid submission to the dictates of the gods to self-sufficiency based on its ego and this in a very short space of time. This vanity is the danger posed to contemporary human beings, because it is no longer linked to their intellectual state of knowledge production and a condition for proving their efficiency, it only exposes it and this already transforms it, as if by magic, into absolute truth, because science has become the new religious doctrine, taking for itself all the dogmas lost by its great historical adversary. This ends up being the most dangerous principle that stands in the way of human beings at this historical moment, because it makes them hostage to another type of belief, much more aggressive than the previous one.

Freedom of thought and the power to decide on new ways of making things happen has always been a frightening challenge for man. If he remained faithful to traditions, it was because, in addition to fear, there were other peculiarities that made him fear innovating without first trying to think about the possible consequences of his actions. And, this tendency towards paranoid conservatism has its roots deep in the past. Convinced that magical acts and rituals influenced the work of nature, man in Antiquity continued, faithfully, to make and use the same things and avoided any changes, so that he did not need to “fear the unknown power that a new form could possess” (KATZENSTEIN , 1986, p. 40).

Man and all his actions and thoughts were totally dependent on the gods. He feared them mercilessly, therefore, he feared that if the formulas of the rites were changed, they would become angry and destroy them. And, in the wake and shadow of this insane fear, many individuals were killed for simply innovating ideas and processes that did not go unpunished from the envy of their opponents. Behind the laws and the divine commandment was the cowardice and real fear of the priest and commander of the phratry of losing power, of being deposed, of having to deal with something about which he had no knowledge; Without this, you wouldn't be able to manipulate it in your favor.

Sacred cows ¹¹exist in all times and places. What is strange is, in the 21st century, when we already have a very broad vision of the precepts of research and academic rigor, admitting the creation of ideas and figures that become untouchable and, for which no type can be created. of criticism, as if this represented a blasphemous act. It ends, therefore, that what has been put

¹¹ For Hindus, the cow is a sacred animal . This gave rise to the expression *sacred cow* , literally, *sacred cow* , to refer to any institution, custom or idea that is highly respected, in an exaggerated and irrational way, treated as if it were above any suspicion or criticism.

into education is not about science, because if that were the case, all ideas, hypotheses and theories would be peaceful objects of discussion regarding their respective conditions for solving the problems posed by society to the scientific community. In this regard, do you refer to the thoughts of Nietzsche (1844-1900) when he asks what mysteries they try to hide when broad discussion about historical and sociological processes is not allowed?

Science does not have the mission to discover the truth; this is understatement and ignorance about the role of scientific research. Its mission is, through the empirical action of serious scientists committed to research, to shed light on what lies between what is understood and what is misunderstood, clarifying them to the point that they can be better analyzed, better interpreted and, consequently, better understood. Once this is achieved, there is the possibility of producing deeper syntheses, which makes knowledge advance in a broader and more enlightening direction.

In Antiquity, human beings persisted in keeping their performances tied to the priest's thoughts because of fear of the gods, who would condemn them to death; but, nowadays, nothing has changed, only the figure of the executioner, because if you dare to go against the dominant thought and the agreed truth, you will end up being placed on the margins of the entire system, being condemned to die of hunger, if you do not surrender yourself to a underemployment or in some work that was not one of their independent choice. If man persisted in maintaining “the same forms of his activities and arts, this is not, as they would have us believe, simply the result of habit and conservatism; but the direct result of active belief in the magical properties of things” (KATZENSTEIN, 1986, p. 40).

This belief comes from the lack of explanation for the natural phenomena that occurred without human knowledge and for which their curiosity did not leave them alone, demanding clarification. With the advent of the will to power that took over the human spirit, it was not difficult for some scoundrel to take such phenomena as a manifestation of the wrath of invisible beings, whom he called gods, and with this, he began his process of obsessive manipulation of other beings who shared of their coexistence, but that, from such acceptance, they became his subjects and servants, because that is what the sacred said and ordered. In this way, it began to be taught to all descendants and ended up becoming an unquestionable truth, maintaining this virtuous model to this day. Things have become so violent that even science, the historical adversary of conventionalism, has become its slave, losing its credibility among the population and, as a way of taking back a position of validity, begins to create strange ideas about something that has the minimum of mastery, presenting ideas and explanations [*which are*

gradually transformed into apparently plausible justifications] capable of convincing individuals who went to school, but who did not learn to think logically.

This means that everyone who enters the walls of a school arrives there with their ready-made ideas about everything and all the phenomena that surround them; therefore, his intention is to receive a formal document that validates what he believes to be fact, to be true. So, why listen to what the teacher has to say? Hegel (1770-1831) could well be called upon to explain the clashes within the classroom, because two experts on the subject (sic) are in combat, the teacher and the student, with the aggravating factor that some supposed theorists of modernity have already advanced that the student is better informed than his teacher *and the majority made a point of agreeing, being convinced that it is true* .

The tragedy only begins, because information is something that may or may not have substantial validity and this is only possible to have value gained after a deep empirical study, in which as many variables as possible are subjected to scientific rigor, being applied to the same Popper's principle of refutability. To achieve the desired end, there is a need for scientific methods of analysis and interpretation, academic preparation and in-depth knowledge of the cause. Unfortunately, neither party is in a position to sustain a discussion because they do not have solid arguments, derived from practice; the student, because he is still a mere apprentice, a being in initial training and the teacher, because he was poorly trained and was forced to believe that, by having a diploma from an institution respected by tradition [and no longer by his academic-scientific *production*] what you were taught [*and not what you learned*] is essential to make you a scholar.

In this way, the eventual and supposed believer in his erudition limits himself to acting within precepts created by the institutional archaic tradition and transmitted by his priests. Thus, “the most trifling innovation attached to its form may lead to danger, release hostile forces, and ultimately produce the ruin of its instigator. Any changes made by manual [*and intellectual*] work can be the cause of the greatest misfortune” (LÉVY-BRUEHL, 1931, p. 776-778 *apud* KATZENSTEIN, 1986, p. 40).

Human beings always face difficulties in dealing, in an orderly manner, with what they do not master, what they do not have sufficient knowledge about; therefore, you stick to what you know, even if you are not satisfied with the results. The study of the behavior of archaic peoples may seem ridiculous, because there is the insidious belief that modern-day men are devoid of superstition and affection, solely for scientific constructions and discoveries.

What allows modern man to refrain from beliefs and some hauntings is the fact that he has a range of information circulating around him in a way that he cannot process and this new

way of seeing himself immersed in an incomprehensible universe binds him to a new perspective; but it doesn't separate him from a laughable past. Before, when he was far from any scientific production and the behavior of nature represented his only way of understanding and comprehending phenomena, it was natural that he created the strangest ways of explaining them. And these explanations were passed on to the following generations who didn't worry about whether it matched reality or not, even because it didn't matter; What mattered was the existence of something that would put an end to that anguish of not knowing or not understanding the phenomenon that was repeated *ad infinitum* and on a regular basis.

What this reveals is that curiosity and the desire to know and understand things is a universal, human attribute, characterized as phylogenetic inheritance and not an event that appears to be a product of modern human thought and, the most interesting thing is that, there are a certain period in human history in which the creation of myths, which are fabulous explanations about the origin of the universe and the organic and mechanical occurrences within it, were drastically reduced, which removed the common human being from the possibility of understanding its existence in the Cosmos.

Nowadays, with all the scientific apparatus and advanced educational training, a condition of egoic exaltation, treated as a historical achievement, is, in contrast, the moment in which the human being finds himself most distant from his empirical reality, understanding nothing or almost nothing. nothing of the universe in which it is inserted. Paradoxically, it is the moment when there is more knowledge about the human brain and its forms of connections, intellectual and epistemological potentialities that all of this has been used to create more deception and falsehoods, lies and promises to search for a new place to live, since this Earth, the home of humans, is doomed to disappear under human hand. All of this makes one wonder if it is no longer viable to build or develop healthier lifestyle strategies that allow nature to have some balance.

The same people who extol human intelligence are already organizing ways to escape when everything falls apart, in other words, the much-vaunted intelligence is being used to escape, to escape death and not to solve a real, present and growing problem. *How much wisdom!* A reptile's brain works with this same ability and there are still those who defend the huge amounts spent on space research, which has taken no one anywhere and guaranteed a future increasingly fraught with feelings of insecurity for everyone.

Of course, with such an expectation of chaos, magic pills emerge that help maintain shape and emotional balance, after all, an exhausted brain cannot feel anguish about the imminent end of the world. To clarify, the human brain processes 40.000 a60,000 thoughts per

day. There is not enough energy for that, any human being would go crazy if the brain had to consciously process such an amount of information. Therefore, most of these thoughts are automated and do not appear in the day's events index and, therefore, when experiencing an experience for the first time, they dedicate a lot of resources to understanding what is happening. As the same experience is repeated, he simply puts his reactions in automatic mode and *deletes* duplicate experiences. Therefore, it already accelerates what is repeated and only processes what is new. However, at school the knowledge is new to the beginner. And this new knowledge does not come to be added to what already exists, it comes to take its place and it is not without a bloody struggle that what already exists loses and gives up its space to the new. Especially because the teacher, accidentally or accidentally [*very implicitly*], transmits the following message: "Forget what you know, distrust common sense and what you have been told and listen to me, because I am going to tell you how things really happen" (PERRENOUD, 2007, p. 28).

The dispute for the power of knowledge is a very old condition and is not linked to modern academia. Sages of all times tried to impose their truths on entire kingdoms and their respective population, and the Catholic Church itself was the absolute holder of all scientific and phenomenological truth for more than ten centuries.

THE CONFLICT BETWEEN TEACHING AND LEARNING

It is not known why someone would be surprised by the arrogance of a teacher in class, if the social contract determines it to be so. And this struggle continues forever and ever in man's life. This suppression of the *old*, of the knowledge already acquired, is understood by the brain as an abortion [*a mental abortion, a loss of a 'cognitium gestatio'*], and it will fight desperately, in order not to lose what it considers as its own pregnancy, for the benefit of another stranger. Human beings are narcissistic by nature. When the master explains his teachings in the classroom, the student resists because he considers what he knows as something intrinsic, *his*; considers that knowledge as born from his insides. Human beings need to have an explanation for everything. If he doesn't have an opinion on the subject, *he imports* someone else's opinion or simply *invents* an explanation.

Another reason for students' resistance to learning is the fact that they may find themselves fixated on the anal phase due to parental retaliation during this period, such as when children start to play with their feces and parents say that they *stink*. The impression they are left with is that what comes out of them is rotten, disgusting, fetid, rubbish. Therefore, at school,

when a student brings work to the teacher and he fails it brutally, the teacher tends to receive confirmation and engrave in his head that everything that comes out of him is rubbish, an object of horror, of aversion. . Hence, the first step in inhibiting academic production by the student and their respective loss of motivation for school and life, consequently.

The mess and rebelliousness among students is due to this historical resistance to the new. This is because this new person will confront the knowledge they bring from their homes. The organizing logic of any system of ideas is resistance to information that does not suit you or that you cannot assimilate. And this confrontation has two aspects: sociological and psychological.

Taking into account the need that society has to obtain a plausible and even bizarre answer about everything (as long as they have it) and, *in the Western vernacular it is not common to differentiate 'unexplained' from 'inexplicable' and even some souls suppose it to be the 'unlimited' knowledge and still others argue, energetically, that a scientist who does not have the answer to everything they want to know is incompetent.*

Katzenstein (1986, p. 65) argues that, “the invention of the apparently simplest instrument made by man requires a complex intellectual process [...]” and he could not be more right, because first of all, one must have contact with challenging situations, in which they impose the need for new technologies and new instruments so that production can be more comprehensive and/or the problem can be solved, making production systems more efficient. No idea appears in the individual's thought coming from nowhere, as if by an oracular message. Contact with the realities of work awakens *insights* that can result in something that can be applied to everyday procedures. Therefore, the new is always a challenge and not necessarily challenging, because this condition is linked to the mechanisms of empirical development.

Human intellectual capacity and potential needs to be, at all times, motivated and driven, because otherwise, it remains parked without any parameter of evidence, in addition to the fact that contact with challenging situations, combined with the freedom to develop creative processes, space to test them and mechanisms to check the results obtained. Creating something new goes far beyond producing something that didn't exist until now; This product must prove useful to society, because otherwise it is a superfluous element with no social value, even if it can be shown, from an aesthetic point of view, as a work of art. The extent to which an innovation can add value to the lives of those who use it, in terms of saving time, money and agility in processes, as well as clarifying previously obscure points in scientific studies is what is advocated with any and all technological advances, not importing the area of concentration.

The most interesting thing about all this is that the judgment must be given by those who use the created tools and not by those who created them, even because in the schizophrenic thinking of its creator, it is perfect, something like a substitute for the [perfect] *son* who did not have. This is somewhat complex, because the empirical realities where the elements will be applied are distinct, by existential nature, and there is no way to create something that responds, adequately and satisfactorily, to all individual and local, particular and singular needs.

This is a point in education that needs to be explored in depth, because it has not been taught how to analyze things according to the reality in which they will be applied and when reference is made using the word reality, it is represented as a variant, carrying within it meanings such as space, time, culture, elements that differ in themselves. Unfortunately, it is only possible to know the applicability of something and its functionality after being tested on the target objects or problem situations that you want to solve. This is why analysis and interpretation techniques, induction and deduction, responses to stimuli are studied, essays in different fields of knowledge are read and research work carried out in different countries and cultures. What is possible in one place may not be possible in another, due to different factors, and it is up to the scholar to discover such obstacles and intervene in their solution, in the most creative way possible.

There are people who are so deeply rooted in their knowledge, *and this will happen at all educational levels, without the slightest distinction*, that there is a serious risk [*even death*] for anyone who questions such knowledge. This fact will occur in two distinct educational instances: The first will be when the 'creator' of the idea is illiterate and/or layman. Furthermore, the average human being is so lazy to think that, when a profound subject is brought to light for discussion and argumentation, when it appears to be profound, difficult to understand, of a high degree of complexity, most people shy away by saying: *It's God's mystery!* , meaning that the *mystery of God* , once it is a mystery, must continue to be a mystery, because if it were not to be a mystery, God himself would have already revealed it. Therefore, it cannot be unraveled and even its argument constitutes profanation, blasphemy. But behind this sacrilege lies the sentence imposed by mediocrity: *I hate thinking! And I hate, even more, those who force me to think!* ; by extension, in a short time, they begin to hate those who think, for the simple fact that they think, because the expression of a thought contradictory to what the *establishment* defines and decrees as excellent truth is already configured and categorized as a hate crime.

According to Galbraith (*sd . apud* LEVITT and DUBNER, 2007, pp. 81-2) , this happens because, accidentally or occasionally, “we associate truth with convenience; that which most intimately promises to avoid great discomfort or an undesirable upheaval. We also

consider anything that helps to increase our self-esteem to be highly acceptable. (...) we cling, as if it were a boat, to the ideas that represent our point of view.”

It is very comfortable to take as truth what suits one's personal project and along with this, there is the pride of many who believe they are the absolute owners of knowledge. Conventionalism is the worst evil for the sciences, because it creates a paradigm based on the beliefs of a few and not on the results of in-depth investigations carried out under scientific guidance. As a curse arising from this type of thinking that does not dare to challenge existing knowledge, there is the creation of a type of truth that remains as such not because of its power of enlightenment and scientific transparency, but because it pleases a small group that is locupletata with this infamous construction of strange ideas. They start by taking fragments of research results and from them, they develop the most insane and unreasonable hypotheses that are only accepted by the population because of the mere fact that their knowledge on the subject comes from common knowledge, a product of magic enhanced by ignorance . [almost] absolute on the topic.

This has become the greatest surprise of formal education, in which science is no longer a product of systematic investigation and peer judgment, until its validity and pragmaticity is confirmed, to become a product of the discourse of those who decide that their truth be taken as real science.

This procedure plunges the entire population into the darkness of pseudoscience and the illusion of a knowledge that is not supported by facts, creating the most cunning and bizarre rhetoric [not to say that they are the *ultimate expression of the height of ridicule*] and in this game of [systematic misinformation, we have the formation of a generation that finds itself prevented from thinking, firstly because it is unnecessary, the answers are there, in front of anyone who wants to understand them; secondly because it became a crime against honor to doubt the results presented by individuals dressed in white pajamas and dressed up as scientists.

Everything that is intended to be exposed as a result of research (sic) is already flawed and the result can already be anticipated even by those who are not skeptics, given the amorphous and biased nature that has taken place and, the explanations for the phenomena, a Since there is no theory that can be applied, they are still incipient and ineffective, leaving nothing more than conjectures and speculations without foundation or reason for being. Not even hypotheses are suggested, in such a way that the culprit for the crisis is faced with reality, standing out and as nothing can be done about him, the solution is to live with misfortune and misfortune, once again using a whole discourse obvious way to cover up a problem that has been going on for decades and for which the solution is worse than living with evil. It turns out

that there comes a point where the evil itself demands a solution and what has been done is to apply another palliative substitute and so on, always in such a way that the measure applied pleases the Greeks and Trojans.

Mechanisms were created that seek to serve everyone and with this, school and education lost all sense of being a center of excellence. To solve this problem, opinion works are published, not scientific research, produced at the mercy of pen by figures exalted by the media with this purpose in which the results lead to affirming what has been conventionally taken as absolute truth.

The principles of identity, diversity and autonomy redefine the relationship to be maintained between education systems and schools. This proposal should not be understood as an absence or omission of the State, because it was so agreed. On the contrary, the identity and autonomy of schools are exercised in the context constituted by general guidelines for action and advice on the implementation of educational policies, which is required of educational systems (federal, state or municipal), so that autonomy is not configured as neglect or abandonment, the definition of guidelines for an educational policy that reflects the needs and demands of the system, in line with the National Guidelines and the structuring of supervision/advisory mechanisms, monitoring and evaluation of school performance results. In the end, it's all just rhetoric.

Currently, we seek to educate through skills and, “competence is the ability to act effectively in a certain type of situation, supported by knowledge, but without being limited to it” (PERRENOUD, 1999, p. 07).

Difficult task. After all, the impartial human mind blindly believes that what went right or wrong in theory or in a given field situation will be doomed to eternal immutability, that is, it will work out in any other place, in any other situation, in any other situation. time, at any other time. The correction to this thought presumes the factual teaching of research as an aspect of experimentation and analysis of the phenomena that occurred until sufficient knowledge is achieved so that safer directions for the teacher's didactic-pedagogical praxis can be determined.

Treated differently, everything that happens in the classroom becomes an object of boredom and supposed theories that only aim to exchange accusations that do not lead to any real improvement for those involved. On the one hand, there are teachers complaining about the students' indifference, their apathy towards systematic content and on the other, students claiming that what is being taught does not make any sense to them, since they do not know when or how they will use such material. knowledge and expertise. The third way created by the *system's experts* is the one in which they seek to prove the student's point, criticizing both

the system, without doing anything to change it or its course and, in the same way, criticizing teachers who act in an authoritarian way . With this, what remains is a student increasingly endorsing his conventional wisdom, adjusting to what suits him, without the slightest condition of understanding the reality that surrounds him, because he is incapable of analyzing it; in fact, he even does so, but always in such a way that his considerations end up proving that he is right about what he defends.

Situations and actions like these, increasingly common in universities and also plaguing secondary classes, are not capable of training a competent student; at most it produces someone who has abilities [*a little*] above average, but who does not attract the attention of [*almost*] anyone because he ends up constantly either victimizing himself or accusing others outside his sphere of every type of aggression he knows. There is a lot to clarify about the issue of competence and how it is formed or consolidated in the human individual and, to everyone's sadness, it is not at school that it emerges nor is it imposed. It is a complex process that takes place based on the capacity of individual intellectuality and through mechanisms of applicability to problem situations that exist and require a solution.

An individual can prove to be much more competent when they know how to manage conflicts and seek solutions, through their team or well-prepared professionals, delegating actions and tasks than, themselves, finding solutions to the challenges posed by their work careers. In education, this is a situation that appears all the time, because working conditions are long-term and everything that happens, from the emergence of the problem situation to its outcome must be recorded, so that in future situations analogues to have somewhere to turn as a starting point for studies and primary analysis.

A teacher must be an individual with great intelligence, because even if he has extensive knowledge of the content he teaches, he does not know what type of interpretation his students will make about the subject and/or the object studied and from there different questions may arise, some are easy to answer, others are very complex and will prove to be a major challenge, sometimes taking years to clarify them objectively.

The definition that has been given for *competence* is something determined by how little or little one knows how to do, such as performing circus tricks, as if this represented a high capacity to think about complex and distinct things. First of all, one must apply one's intellect and, for this, one needs motivation and expectations of feedback on this action, something that does not always occur and this ends up in frustration and not in the development of new techniques. academic creativity and production.

Specifically, for a teacher, being competent does not mean having mastery of teaching techniques and content, it is necessary to know how to guide students to develop their searches autonomously and, sometimes, independently. The richness of a class lies in the academic discussions on deep and complex topics, for which there are still no objective answers, which does not invalidate the training process, given that what matters is not the moment but an entire future existence. and what value it can add to the scientific and social fields.

The secret of a good class is in properly directing the student's thinking to seek viable solutions to their questions and, once found, not submitting to them as being the revealed truth but rather an answer that should be, herself, subjected to severe scrutiny and judgment value.

Many confuse didactics with methodology and in this process end up adopting disastrous practices created from the thoughts of some scholar [*who knows what*] who decided to express some knowledge about forms of learning and thus believes that the method he is directing to its audience is ideal, if not, correct and will have the desired effect on parents and teachers [*completely unprepared for the job*] which is total, immediate, perfect and harmonious learning.

We must begin by understanding that fear has become the great villain of contemporary society, in which parents who want their children to achieve a good position in society expect them to learn from an early age everything they will need in adult life. There are two complex problems to face, without much chance of solution, the first of which is that what parents feel is not desire but anxiety, produced by the fear that another child will achieve the knowledge necessary for such a field and their child no. The second factor is that, with technological advances, the pride of saying that we know how the brain works, in its full materiality, has been created and in the wake of this nonsense disguised as scientificity, they are creating bizarre teaching methods and parents don't care. , because they believe they are doing the best for their children in relation to their futures as professionals.

Human learning is something that is directly linked to the brain-cognitive maturation process in which lived experiences are assimilated and accommodated until they provoke discussions and questions and, the more the child feels free to question, knowing that they will have If your doubts are clarified by your mentor, you will seek to advance towards knowledge.

No learning occurs immediately; there is an entire process of thought formation that is crossed by culture, by the load of information that surrounds the individual's existence, by customs, by tradition, by superstitions, through experience and self-knowledge, which are explanations that are created as a response to the phenomena that permeate everyone's existence, in an unquestionable way and these are the ones that will present the most resistance

throughout life, because they are interpreted by the individual himself as an inviolable private heritage, therefore, any explanation to the contrary is understood as an offense guys.

When you think and still defend that learning must be perfect, immediate and harmonious, you are creating a model doomed to the most imminent failure, because no learning occurs perfectly; hence the need to always review the knowledge acquired and the way in which it is interpreted, because this leads to mistaken understandings and understandings in line with the time, culture and values of each time, in particular. The search for new mechanisms and methods of analyzing knowledge is a demonstration that what is known must be subjected to experimentation in search of new meanings or confirmation of the meanings that are theoretically adopted.

No learning is harmonious, because knowledge of the new awakens and provokes conflicts of all kinds and so it must be, because harmony is consensus and all of this is marked by the dictatorship of single thought, absolute certainty and the absence of questioning about ways to see the same object and/or phenomenon from another angle.

Rubem Alves is not wrong when he criticizes the education system based on positivism, in which the childish belief that repetition of the act leads to learning and mastery is maintained. He states that “ the study of grammar does not make poets. Harmony study does not make composers. The psychology study does not make balanced people. The study of 'educational sciences' does not make educators” (Idem, 2013, sp).

It must always be clarified that every being that is born is first generated in some matrix and the healthier it is, the more powerful the being will be born. Even though Rubem Alves wanted to say that it is not possible to build educators/teachers, where they will find mechanisms to become masters, knowledgeable about teaching practices, how their object of work thinks, feels, how it is carried out... The study of specific areas may not produce geniuses in their respective fields; However, without knowledge and mastery of the techniques related to each professional's areas of activity, the result is tremendous confusion and a waste of time and money, and worse, individuals who will tend to believe that they are great just because they studied with figures immaculate by the media.

The entire process of studying techniques and operations provides discipline to the student and, subsequently, to the professional. There are many variables that make up any system and anyone who intends to take a certain career as their field of activity must, at least, know them and be aware of the challenges that eventually arise in addition to those that are inherent parts of the ordinary process of construction and acquisition of knowledge itself.

TO THINK ABOUT DIDACTIC TRANSPOSITION IN LEARNING

Teaching, in a didactic way, is a very complex task, because it requires knowledge about the object of study and preparation so that the content is clear enough to awaken and encourage in the student the desire to go beyond what was presented during the lecture. classroom. This is the reason that leads to the understanding that being a teacher is not just the exercise of teaching; it is an inherent search for a becoming that is not complete and each time the desired answers are found [*even if partially*], new ones appear, without even the previous ones having been clarified and it is through this continuous process of investigation that it has the essence of education, that is, it is in constant movement.

Many things need to be learned, along the way, by those who intend to pursue a teaching career; however, what has been seen is a feeling of accommodation on the part of teachers and is not a state of laziness or stagnation; It's something strange, as if they were convinced that with all the technological equipment available to them it would be enough to build a generation of dedicated thinkers capable of reading the world in which they are inserted and interpreting it according to the essential standards for a full and challenging life, capable of leading to overcoming.

This has been the big mistake of the present, that of making people believe that the answers are ready, with just a click to access them and, with this, knowledge is no longer restricted to long and endless years of study and dedication. but rather learning which button to press in order to obtain the appropriate response to the solution to the problem posed. With this, the meaning of formal education, of the professional teacher and of the educator, the one who will take care of directing the student towards a technical and epistemic discipline, carrying out his didactic trajectory of development between Episteme and *Phrónesis* , *disappears* .

Good educators are born when the system offers ideal conditions for them to emerge, develop their role with mastery and mature in the respective fields chosen for professional activity. It is not by motivating individuals to become teachers that they will become teachers; There must be something more, a possibility that the charm of the chosen profession will bring about a transformation in their lives. Without this perspective, there are nothing more than mercenaries or refugees from hunger and failure camping or even parachuting into the area of formal education.

The perception of the world that a given individual has cannot be defined by their level of academic training, because this would be giving formal education a possibility and potential

to provide miracles, such as the transformation of people and feelings through brute force, magic... or which is unthinkable within proper logic.

First of all, it is necessary for individuals to understand the semantic meaning of politics, so that later their social understanding becomes possible and how it can influence them in decision-making, which does not reduce the possibilities of errors and failures. Over a relatively short period of time, two distinct groups have been created that do not communicate with each other, they only live to highlight the worst things one and the other do, without ever proposing a viable solution and that is where we have the same situation . of the classroom reproducing itself in society, in which no one understands or understands what is happening and, someone always appears to make a mediocre and backwards interpretation and the result is anarchy and, as is only natural, the State has of resorting to violence to combat it, becoming a cruel tyrant, which results in nihilism.

Thinking everyone thinks; however, in a wrong, raw way, without improvements to the senses and reason for being. But what would be a correct way of thinking? Again, there is the presumption of wanting to hold the magical, correct and perfect formula on how everyone [*without exception*] should proceed, which is still this desire, a discreet form of tyranny. So, is education tyrannical? The answer would be yes; but, due to the fact that its semantic and social meaning is confused, to highlight, the discipline, the doctrine, the norm, the interest is to create an individual based on the ideology of the State. Therefore, if education creates individuals with an anarchic spirit, it is for the simple fact that the dominant ideology in the State is based on the absence of law, that is, on an *anomic State* .

Education cannot be understood as an instrument for bringing about change, because that is not what it has been used for. Its ideal is the maintenance of order, safeguarding and protecting the law and when this is lost in time and space, it is urgent to protect tradition, because it serves to remind individuals of their phylogenetic history, the evolutionary history of the species.

Through education, one can think, in a profound way, about what is best for society on its path towards the ideal future, always desired, and this is the responsibility of poets and creative artists, not the task of teachers. The way it has been conducted, the school's destiny is to be emptied, because in a very short time, everyone [*with very few exceptions*] will lose confidence in the formal educational system and there will be a return to tribal educational models.

School knowledge and, by its extension, academic knowledge, which generate, as a consequence, school subjects, do not constitute a direct didactic transposition of scientific

knowledge to school subjects. They represent organized and didactically ordered knowledge, classified by degrees of difficulty and aimed at heterogeneous audiences, with different ages and cognitive abilities. Therefore, the purposes and objects of school subjects are completely different from the references of scientific subjects, not being in line with what is required for a full existence and the formation of a level of intelligence that is necessary for this historical moment. Scientific logic is shared by both types of discipline; however, this does not make them identical.

Contemporary education is undergoing several reforms. And one of them is the unfolding of its conceptual functions. The concept of education restricted to a reserved group of individuals is already unthinkable in this century, where knowledge is available to everyone. But, educating without repressing or destroying what is already composed is something that really provokes reflections and doubts; something also unthinkable, even because there can be no knowledge without destruction; because, to learn something new, it is necessary to analyze the contents that supported the thinking and which, given the discoveries, can now be considered old, obsolete, outdated.

Here is a new order presented by M. Foucault: teaching the subject not to be what he is. Complicated? It's a bit; but, let's see how much: when Aristotle (384-322 BC) defined his policy, he outlined it from the perspective that the subject would be condemned to be what he was, without conditions or possibilities of changing the status quo, because the *Fates* thus they had decided it would be. However, we no longer live under Aristotelian laws that decide our lives in such a strict way, because the discussion between *Physis* and *Nomòs*, although not closed, no longer fits in a time where human laws, ratified in secularism, override natural laws and with their institutionalization, social mobility ended up creating such a system that man is free to disbelieve in his destiny traced by the Fates and predicted by the Oracles.

When an educational precept is defined, one automatically thinks about the integral formation of man, that is, solid pedagogical procedures that aim at responsibility, which is the same as showing the most correct path to follow, even if this is not the most easy. Several authors say that man is unable to carry out his own catharsis, his self-analysis, others still claim that man *must* internalize himself. The right measure of quanta is the deliberate desire to create a society that respects the human being as an individual. By individualization, it is clear that the being must fight for a society that accepts what is different, that allows doubt, that considers man as a man and not as a treacherous and murderous wild beast; but at the same time, do not neglect your psychological security against the abuse that comes from those who wish to control

all the feelings and desires of their peers, in the name of beautiful and wonderful things, which only serve as scarecrows.

CONCLUSION

Education aims to train man, that is, to work on him from the inside out, building a being that will be a source of pride for his parents and the country. Hercules, after becoming an adult, had the opportunity to make his choice about which path to follow. In his adolescence, after killing his lyre teacher, as he was under the tutelage of his father, he sent him to the countryside to be educated by the Centaur Chiron. And why for a being that was half animal and half man? Exactly so that he could learn to master both parts that coexist in his being. However, just as man is above the horse, reason must be above emotions and wild instincts. The very vision and understanding of education 'as a social transformative agent' is still an extremely young concept. In the beginning it was for the poor, the boys wanted to be gladiators, because it was the superiority of muscular strength that decided who had possession of things or who made their will prevail. Muscular strength was soon supplemented and replaced by instruments: the winner was the one who had the best weapons or the one who demonstrated the greatest skill in handling them [*thus, the sons of nobles learned the art of cavalry and the sword from an early age. Only nobles could be knights, which was equivalent to fighting on horseback*].

From the moment weapons were introduced, intellectual superiority began to replace brute force. And, it was only with the advent of Protestantism that there was a greater scope of education, which was expanded with the advent of the Industrial Revolution. Currently, the socializing role of education is held in high regard, especially because the concept of citizen has expanded to the Cosmos and is not just restricted to the city walls.

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